

NOTES ON THE LADYBIRD BEETLE SPIDER *PARAPLECTANA WALLERI* (BLACKWALL, 1865) FROM SABI SAND GAME RESERVE, SOUTH AFRICA

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Abstract

The genus *Paraplectana* Brito Capello, 1867 are known from Africa and Asia. With their bright colours they mimic beetle species belonging to the family Coccinellidae. A *Paraplectana walleri* (Blackwall, 1865) female was observed over a three day period at the Sabi Sand Game Reserve that lies adjacent to the Kruger National Park, in the Lowveld of Mpumalanga. This is the first observations on their web building and feeding behaviour.

Key words: Cyrtarachninae, behaviour, predation, moths, taxonomy.

Introduction

A yellow Ladybird beetle spider was discovered by the first author while working as a field guide at Dulini, a lodge in Sabi Sand Wildtuin that lies adjacent to the Kruger National Park, in the Lowveld of Mpumalanga, South Africa. The spider was discovered while walking through the bush early one morning. Photographs of the specimen was taken and it was identified as *Paraplectana walleri* (Blackwall, 1865) also known as Waller's Ladybird spider of the family Araneidae (Figs 1,2).

Members of *Paraplectana* belong to the subfamily Cyrtarachninae a group of spiders known for their adapted orb-webs. Members of this subfamily construct "spanning thread-webs", a basic orb web, but the web's diameter, sticky spiral spacing and viscid thread diameter differ from that of typical orb webs. The viscid threads are studded with large droplets. Each of the short threads between the radii is known as a spanning thread, and is unique in that it breaks when prey comes into contact with it. The prey flies into the web, gets stuck to a viscid thread, the thread breaks, and the spider pulls the prey up to the hub of the web to feed (Stowe, 1986; Tanikawa *et al.* 2014). In South Africa two other species are known to make spanning thread webs namely *Cyrtarachne ixoides* (Simon, 1870) (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones 2008) and *Pasilobus dippenaarae* Roff & Haddad, 2015.

Paraplectana walleri is an African endemic described by (Blackwall, 1865) as *Eurysoma walleri* from Mozambique. The species is known from West, Central and Southern Africa and Madagascar. In South Africa, it is recorded from the Eastern Cape, Mpumalanga and KwaZulu-Natal. With their round, bright yellow bodies decorated with black spots they resemble members of the Night shade Ladybird beetle (*Epilachna paykulli*) of the family Coccinellidae (Picker *et al.* 2003). These beetles secrete a fluid from joints in their legs, which gives them a foul taste. This and their bright colours warn would-be attackers like birds to ignore them.

Fig. 1 *Paraplectana walleri* female dorsal view observed on the bark of a Acacia tree.

Fig. 2 *Paraplectana walleri* female ventral view .

Study area

A *Paraplectana walleri* female was observed in the field at Dulini, a lodge in Sabi Sand Wildtuin. This is the first observations on their web building behaviour. The area was marked and protected to prevent interference of elephants. The area **was observed for three days** The spider was found on a wild mint bush that was situated next to an Acacia tree (Fig. 3a-c).

Results

Observations started on 6 May 2020 at 18:10. The spider was resting on a Wild Mint bush (*Mentha longifolia* L.) (Fig. 3b). At 18:25 the spider started to construct a web by releasing a 3 m length of silk thread. The thread was carried by the wind and it attach to the lower branches of the Wild Mint. At 18:45 another thread attached to dried grass about 42 cm away. At 19:32 the spider moved around the leaves and flowers of the Wild Mint. She parasailed down with a silk thread (Fig. 4), but climbed fast back up again. She lay down silk threads around the vegetation, moving back and forth from Wild Mint to grass without using the main strand of web (Fig. 5). At 19:39 the female was hanging upside down in the web; on 19:45 she add more silk thread in between main strands. At 19:48 she was again observed hanging upside down in same spot. The wind was then picking up and on 21:01 a moth landed on the web but the spider moved in the opposite direction and the moth broke free. At 21:05 she checked the web but at 21:12 she is affected by the strong wind and was only hanging in the middle of web swaying from side to side. At 23:16 she was on the main web area but there were no further activity.

On 7 May at 03:00 she was feeding on a moth; she wraps the moth in silk to form a ball – using her pedipalpi to rotate and chelicerae to crush moths body into smaller size. Nothing was left to waste. She fed while in a upright position. At 04.35 she finished feeding and at 05:52 she started to remove the web by gathering silk threads in her chelicerae (Fig. 6).

Fig. 3 a Study area at Sabi Sand Game Reserve b: Wild mint bush where spider was found c: Arrows indicate areas where spider was constructing her web.

Fig. 4 Female parasails down.

Fig. 6 Female busy removing the old web gathering silk threads in her chelicerae.

Fig. 5 Female *Paraplectana walleri* moving around building the web.

At 06:05 on the 7 May the female left the main web area climbing down to the Wild mint bush area and onto grasses. At 07:08 she moved down into the dense vegetation below the mint bush and took up position underneath a mint leaf where she was not visible from above (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 Female take up position in mint bush during the day.

On the late afternoon of 7 May observations started again. At 17:34 the female was located about 32 cm from ground surface, resting. At 17:52 the night activity starts. At 17:56 she moved upwards towards the *Acacia nilotica* (dead branches). Abseiling down and using silk threads to climb back up; repeated this action about 1.2 m above ground (Fig. 8). Between 18:08 and 23:03 she was moving between the main web area and mint flower bush laying down and inspecting her web (Fig. 9). In between this she rested for short periods. On 8 May at 03.30 the web was in a different spot as before but there were no sign of any kills. At 05:05 she start removing the web again. At 07:05 she moved to her day time resting area in the mint bush (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8 Study area showing the different areas of activity.

On 8 May at 17:54 activity start again. At 18:08 she rapidly started to construct her web with erratic movements, fast abseiling, and return climbing back again (Fig. 9). From 18:19 -21:01 a lot of movement over main web area with spider resting in between. At 21:08 she fell onto the ground while traveling on existing web down to grass, she fell on her back. It took her 48 sec to get back onto her feet. She navigated her way back although slow going. At 21:57 She has reached to top of the Mint Flowers.

Fig. 9 Female abseiling using silk and her legs.

Fig. 10 Moth before it was caught in the web.

Fig. 11 Female feeding on the moth.

She then caught a moth (Fig. 10) that is caught in the web. She holds onto her kill and used her pedipalpi to rotate the prey before consuming start. The feeding finished at 22:32. (Fig. 11).

On 9 May at 05:10 we could not find the spider only webbing on plants still visible. The area was again revisited between 9-11 May but the spider could not be found.

Conclusion

Little is still known about the behaviour of many spiders in South Africa especially species of rare genera such as *Paraplectana* genus. This is our first record of their behaviour in South Africa. We now know they are active at night, and makes a spanning thread web, feed on moths and they are found in low vegetation and possible mimics the Night shade Ladybird beetle that is also a low vegetation inhabitant.

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